

Brushless Excitation Solutions for Wound-Field Synchronous Motors in Electric Vehicles: a Survey

Murtaza Ali Khooharo
DESTEC
University of Pisa
Pisa, Italy
m.khooharo@studenti.unipi.it

Luca Papini
DESTEC
University of Pisa
Pisa, Italy
luca.papini@unipi.it

Paolo Bolognesi
DESTEC
University of Pisa
Pisa, Italy
paolo.bolognesi@ing.unipi.it

Abstract—Electric vehicles can produce far less pollution than conventional fuel-based vehicles. Nevertheless, their manufacturing still involves issues about sustainability from both environmental and economical points of view, also concerning the use of rare earths for permanent magnets. Therefore, the use of popular Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machines (PMSMs) is increasingly questioned despite their high efficiency, compactness, and light weight. There is a growing interest in alternative solutions for electric motor technologies. Among them, wound-field synchronous motors (WFSMs) stand out as a promising option featuring high power density and operational flexibility thanks to full field control. However, the conventional use of sliprings and brushes to supply the field winding affects both reliability and maintenance, turning out to be a potentially significant drawback. This paper provides an overview and comparison of the main solutions proposed to eliminate such sliding contacts, highlighting their respective benefits and limitations.

Index Terms—Electric Vehicles, Wound Field Synchronous Motors, Brushless Excitation, Wireless Power Transfer.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric vehicles (EVs) are revolutionizing transportation by replacing fossil-powered engines and related fuel tanks with electric motors and rechargeable batteries. This shift can permit to eliminate tailpipe emissions, thus significantly contributing to a cleaner environment especially in metropolitan areas. Moreover, EVs can achieve lower running costs as they require less maintenance compared to traditional vehicles while electricity can also be cheaper than fossil fuels [1]. Furthermore, the much better torque profile made available by electric motors translates into a silent and smooth but also very responsive and rewarding driving experience. As more and more countries plan to phase out the sale of new petrol and diesel cars, the International Energy Agency report 2022 predicted that by 2030 there will be 145 million electric vehicles on the road [2]. However, while the polluting emissions related to the operation of electric vehicles are obviously far lower than their conventional equivalents, when considering the impact of manufacturing processes and the supply chain the transition may turn out less beneficial. In fact, the overall carbon emissions involved in the manufacturing process of

the different parts of an electric vehicle are estimated to be higher than for a comparable conventional vehicle, although the overall outcome is still favorable when looking at the whole Life-Cycle-Assessment (LCA) [3]. In the last decades, Permanent Magnets (PMs) have been increasingly used in electric machines for various applications, including EVs, renewables, industry applications etc., as they permit to reduce volume, weight and losses. [4]. In fact, according to the report of IDTechEx 2023, approximately 85% of the motors used in EVs are PM motors, followed by 12% of AC induction motors (ACIM) and 3% Wound Field Synchronous Machines (WFSM). However, high-performance PMs require rare-earth materials, determining a significant environmental impact for mining and manufacturing: in particular, Neodymium and Dysprosium play crucial roles for the much-renowned NdFeB PMs [5]. Moreover, most of active mines and manufacturing plants for rare earths and permanent magnets are located in, or controlled by, very few countries: this poses serious risks concerning both actual availability and price, since the recycling capability is still very limited. In fact, their cost is pretty high and unpredictable: for example, recently raw Nd was priced about 100 US\$/kg in comparison to about 8 US\$/kg for Cu [6]. Therefore, despite high-end PMs can provide clear technical benefits permitting to create more compact, lightweight and efficient electric machines, their procurement still remains a bottleneck in terms of sustainability, from both an environmental and an economic point of view.

Consensus is then growing about the necessity to reduce or eliminate the utilization of rare-earth PMs for mass and environmental-sensitive applications, such as propulsion motors for EVs. A report published by [7] highlights that several major European automotive manufacturers are currently preferring rare earth-free motor designs, mainly WFSMs and induction motors. For example, Renault is using a WFSM produced by Continental in their Renault Zoe EV using classical brushes and sliprings are used for field winding supply, whereas BRUSA Elektronik AB has introduced a 160 kW peak power WFSM featuring an inductive power transfer solution [8].

On the other hand, the use of machines not featuring PMs could permit to achieve an higher operational flexibility. In fact, in Fig.1 the typical powertrain architecture of a single-

Funded by the European Union, Grant 101072580. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EU MSCA Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

motor EV is depicted, highlighting that it is supplied by the battery through a converter and, in general, it is connected to the wheels via a transmission system. The situation is similar for multi-motor vehicles. In any case, the power capability of the battery can be made available for propulsion in a wide range of vehicle speed, as ideally desirable, only when either the transmission features a suitably controllable gear ratio, or the motor features a large operational area above base speed. The latter could permit to use a fixed-ratio transmission system, which is much simpler, inexpensive and reliable, or even to adopt a direct-drive solution. However, this requires that the motors are able to efficiently operate in a broad field-weakening region. From such point of view, the machines not featuring PMs, such as WFSM, induction and switched reluctance, have an inherent advantage [9].

Fig. 1. Block diagram of powertrain of an electric vehicle

II. WOUND FIELD SYNCHRONOUS MOTORS

In recent years, the interest in WFSMs for EV applications has significantly increased as they are deemed to be an attractive alternative to PMSMs [10]. In fact, WFSMs are equipped with a dedicated field winding to take care of the machine magnetization instead of using PMs. This permits to achieve significant torque density and efficiency at full load, while a proper design permits to significantly extend the useful speed range above base speed by simply adjusting the field current without resorting to specific field weakening techniques as required by PMSMs. This allows for the optimization of motor operation in real-time based on driving demands, improving efficiency and driving experience even in EVs featuring a fixed-ratio transmission. Moreover, WFSMs can achieve a good level of efficiency across a broader operating range compared to other motor types such as induction motors [11]. This translates into improved energy consumption and a potentially longer driving range for EVs. In vehicles where space is constrained, the smaller size of WFSMs made possible by their torque density can be advantageous. When properly designed, WFSMs also feature a pretty robust construction and good reliability, especially compared to some types of PMSMs [12]. In fact, PMs can incur in demagnetization due to high temperature, high inverse field and vibrations.

Nevertheless, in WFSMs the field winding is located on the rotor, so brushes and sliprings are traditionally used to supply it as shown in Fig. 2 [13]. This turns into a weak point: in fact, sliding contacts generate friction and Joule losses while

also incur in wearing, producing conductive particulate and occasional sparking; therefore, brushes also demand regular maintenance.

Fig. 2. Conventional sliprings-brushes solution for WFSM

Several solutions have been proposed to eliminate slips and brushes from WFSMs, which can be classified into 4 main categories according to their operation principle (see Fig.3): coaxial auxiliary generator, embedded auxiliary windings, and contactless electromagnetic power transfer based on either inductive or capacitive coupling.

Fig. 3. Contactless solutions for WFSM excitation

In the following sections, such solutions are recalled and commented on, highlighting strengths and weaknesses.

III. POWER SUPPLY FROM AUXILIARY GENERATOR

The elimination of sliprings and brushes to supply the rotating field winding of WFSMs was first addressed referring to their application as generators [14]. The proposed solution consisted of modernizing the classical concept of producing the required power by means of a coaxial auxiliary generator: a synchronous machine featuring an inverted structure, i.e. a rotary armature and a stationary excitation system, is used to supply the field winding of the WFSM by means of a diode rectifier located on the rotor as well. In Fig. 4 a typical scheme of this solution is depicted [15] referring to a typical voltage control application as customary in gensets, highlighting that the excitation current of the WFSM can be indirectly controlled by adjusting the current flowing in the stationary field winding of the auxiliary generator.

Fig. 4. Classical brushless excitation system for WFSM

However, such a solution makes sense in generation applications, where the required mechanical power is provided by the primary engine, and the overall volume is not much of a problem. In propulsion applications it is not very effective because the auxiliary generator would increase the required space and should be driven by the WFSM, leading to a larger, heavier and less efficient system.

IV. POWER TRANSFER VIA EMBEDDED WINDINGS

As a second alternative, power can be transmitted to the rotor also using the existing magnetic structure of the WFSM. Typically, to avoid interfering with the main machine operation, an auxiliary MMF featuring a different number of poles and a different synchronous speed is superimposed on the main MMF distribution. The rotor is therefore equipped with an auxiliary winding designed for the same number of poles, which will be subjected to variable linked flux-inducing voltages. This secondary winding is then connected to the field winding by means of a dedicated rotary converter.

Several solutions have been proposed to implement this concept using different configurations of stator windings, rotor windings, and auxiliary converters [16]. In [17] a solution was proposed consisting of connecting the output terminals of the 3-phase 4-pole armature winding of a WFSM to a diode rectifier, whose DC output feeds an auxiliary stator winding featuring 2 poles. as shown in Fig. 5. In this solution, the voltage induced in the auxiliary rotor winding depends on the armature currents and on the rotor speed, so no field current is available at standstill: this limits the torque at null and low speed to the sole reluctance component eventually available due to the rotor anisotropy. Moreover, the field and armature currents cannot be controlled independently at any given speed.

Fig. 5. High-harmonic injection-based WFSM topology

Another example of harmonic-based field excitation with only one stator winding is shown in Fig.6. [18]. Two MMF distributions are produced by stator windings: one rotates synchronously, whereas the other rotates asynchronously to induce current on an auxiliary set of rotor windings. Furthermore, this approach allows for self-starting from zero speed.

Open armature windings supplied by 2 inverters is another configuration of WFMS that was considered to induce voltages in the auxiliary rotor winding [19].

Overall, the embedded winding method for WFSM excitation presents several challenges that complicate its implementation. Complex harmonic generation within the system

Fig. 6. Configuration with single-phase exciter winding supplied via inverter

requires advanced control strategies to minimize undesirable effects. Magnetic saturation of the core becomes a concern under high excitation levels, further impacting performance. Power losses due to harmonics, including additional eddy current and hysteresis losses, reduce the overall energy efficiency. Rotor heating and thermal management present significant design challenges, particularly under sustained operation. Moreover, most implementations provide poor support for start-up and low-speed operation, where sufficient excitation may be difficult to achieve. Finally, the design complexity and associated costs make this approach less attractive for cost-sensitive applications such as automotive.

V. SEPARATED WIRELESS POWER TRANSFER

Wireless (contactless) power transfer (WPT) is a technology presently used in more and more applications, such as charging of battery operated devices or EVs, supply of moving parts of industrial equipment etc. It consists of dedicated transmitters and receivers linked by high-frequency fields generated in the medium separating the parts, in most of cases air [20]. WPT solutions can be classified into 2 main categories, as illustrated in Fig.7: near field, in which the wavelength of electromagnetic (EM) fields is much greater than the distance between the transmitter and receiver; far field, where the distance is greater or comparable [21]. Some examples of both solutions are discussed in detail in [22].

Fig. 7. Classification of Wireless power transfer methods

Fig. 8. Typical architecture of WPT for WFSM field winding supply

Far field WPT is not much efficient and is more suited for low-power applications, so typically near-field WPT using the general architecture shown in Fig.8 is considered for supplying the field winding of a WFSM. Near-field WPT solutions are further classified according to the field mainly taking care of the power transfer (see Fig.9): inductive when based on magnetic field, capacitive when based on electric field.

Fig. 9. Basic concepts of near-field WPT: a) Inductive, b) Capacitive

A. Inductive Power Transfer

The concept of inductive power transfer consists in using magnetically coupled coils operated in AC similarly to a transformer, as illustrated in Fig.9.a for the simple and most popular single-phase configuration. Typically, magnetic cores are also used to achieve a more effective transformer operation by confining the main flux path and reducing its reluctance, yet including a gap to preserve the physical separation of the 2 parts that makes possible the relative motion. Such WPT architecture is widely used in applications such as device and EVs charging, near-field communication (NFC), and some medical implants [23].

A popular scheme of such solution for rotary applications is depicted in Fig.10: on the stator side a DC source supplies a high-frequency inverter which in turn feeds the primary coil; on the rotor side, the secondary coil, coupled to the primary via the main airgap, usually supplies the load via a diode rectifier.

Fig. 10. Circuit diagram for a typical inductive coupling solution.

In order to maximize the mutual coupling, the primary and secondary coils are typically located coaxially in close proximity. As shown in Fig.11, 2 main layout variants are usually considered depending on the orientation of the main field lines in the transformer airgap: axial and radial [24], [25].

Some solutions have been already developed up to industrial products, often tightly integrated with the WFSM. For example, based on an axial rotary transformer structure, the "Magnet free EV motor" was developed [26], whose

Fig. 11. Basic rotary transformer layouts: (a) Axial, (b) Radial

layout is depicted in Fig.12. It features a high operation frequency in order to permit reducing the size and weight of the transformer; nevertheless, its placement behind the WFSM rotor may increase the overall volume.

Fig. 12. Industrial product using an external axial rotary transformer [26]

An example of tighter integration is provided by the "In-rotor Inductive-Excited Synchronous Motor" [27]: as shown in Fig.13, the WFSM rotor features a relatively large hollow shaft, inside which a radial rotary transformer is housed in order to save on the overall axial length.

Fig. 13. Industrial product using an embedded radial rotary transformer [27]

In [24] a WFSM equipped with a radial rotary transformer has been designed for hybrid vehicle applications.

Anyway, as the power that has to be transferred to the rotor increases, the simple 1-phase transformer solutions become more and more inefficient. For higher-power applications, multi-phase configurations can then be fruitfully adopted.

In any case, the transformer-based WPT concept suffers from an inherent issue related to the high reluctance of the main flux path deriving from the air gap required to permit the relative motion. In fact, this leads to a magnetization inductance pretty lower than in normal comparable gap-less transformers, both as an absolute value and with respect to

the leakage inductances. This turns into high magnetization current values and high voltage drops, basically forcing to oversize both the converter and the primary coil while also possibly requiring a more attentive control.

Aiming to improve the system performances, the inclusion of capacitors connected in series to the primary and secondary windings as shown in Fig.14 was proposed in order to achieve a resonant operation [28]). In fact, when the resonance condition is met, the energy transfer between the coils is significantly amplified, leading to smaller size requirements and higher efficiency compared to the initial solution.

Fig. 14. Inductive resonant WPT for WFSM applications

Moreover, achieving resonance conditions permits also to turn into soft-switching mode, which can permit to drastically reduce the overall losses and thus also to increase the operation frequency in order to reduce the size and weight of reactive components. An example of soft-switching series resonant WPT system is described in [29], where a remarkable 1 MHz resonance frequency is used. Table I provides a comprehensive summary of the power ratings, switching frequencies, and air gap specifications utilized in various rotary transformer designs as discussed in the existing literature.

Nevertheless, implementing an effective resonance-based WPT system is more complex compared to normal transformer-based operation. In fact, it requires careful design and precise tuning of both the transmitter and receiver circuits in order to achieve optimal performance. Therefore, the system results highly sensitive to the geometry of the airgap between the rotary and stationary components, making precise mechanical alignment essential for consistent performance. Moreover, the control system shall also operate precisely, especially when facing variable load conditions, making frequency tuning and stability critical factors: in fact, even slight deviations can lead to reduced efficiency and improper operation. Furthermore, raising the operation frequency introduces additional losses and higher complexities in the design of electronic boards which necessitates of advanced solutions to achieve reliable performances with acceptable electromagnetic emissions. The control of the WFSM excitation becomes also increasingly complex and possibly slower, requiring sophisticated algorithms to manage varying operating conditions. Finally, electromagnetic emissions (EMI) represent a potential issue as they could impact the operation of the surrounding electronic

systems. Therefore, although WPT based on rotary transformers seems to be a promising solution for WFSM applications, this solution is not widely adopted.

TABLE I
POWER RATING, FREQUENCY AND AIRGAP OF ROTARY TRANSFORMERS DISCUSSED IN LITERATURE

S.NO	Power Rating	Frequency	Air Gap	Refrence
1	Up to 1 kW	50 kHz	0.6 mm	[30]
2	200 W	70 kHz	-	[31]
3	100 W	0.8 kHz/20 kHz	0.3 mm	[32]
4	Up to 1 kW	20 kHz	1 mm	[33]
5	1.2 kVA	25.11, 292.4 kHz	0.8 mm	[34]
6	1.2 kVA	50 Hz	0.4 mm	[35]
7	800 W	800 Hz	0.5 mm	[36]
8	480 W	20.5 kHz	0.6 mm	[37]
9	250 W	50, 400, 1000 Hz	0.3 mm	[25]
10	200 W	70 kHz	-	[38]
11	1000 W	-	0.5 mm	[39]
12	5 kW	-	0.5 mm	[24]
13	1kW	100kHz	1 mm	[40]

B. Capacitive Power Transfer

The Capacitive WPT concept consists in using the electric field to link the transmitter and receiver. For such purpose, the parts are equipped with matching metallic electrodes that, when facing each other separated by the gap, give rise to equivalent capacitors. Such elements are then connected via other components in order to give rise to close circuits that can be AC supplied, according to the conceptual scheme depicted in Fig.9.b for the simplest configuration [41].

The electrodes can feature any shape, provided that an effective capacitive coupling is achieved. A larger number of electrodes and more complex circuit configurations could also be used. For rotary applications, capacitive WPT systems can be also classified according to the direction of the main field lines crossing the gap as axial or radial. Typically, the AC source supplying the capacitive coupling system is constituted by an inverter fed by a DC source, whereas a rectifier is used as interface to provide the DC output.

Capacitive WPT is commonly used in low-power applications such as radio frequency identification (RFID) tags, touchscreens, and some proximity sensors where it can be simpler and less expensive than inductive coupling [42]. Nevertheless, the capacitance of the coupling capacitors represents a bottleneck for the power transfer: in fact, in order to keep reasonably limited voltages, the currents should rise with power, which in turn requires increasing either the capacitance or the frequency. Since the gap thickness usually cannot be reduced too much, increasing the capacitance means increasing the area of facing electrodes and thus ultimately the volume of the device.

The above limits can be addressed by exploiting the properties of resonant circuits: for example, in [43] the use of a capacitive WPT for WFSMs applications was investigated using an auxiliary series inductor as depicted in Fig.15.

In such solution, an inverter is used to provide high frequency AC supply to a series LC circuit constituted by the

Fig. 15. Capacitive resonant WPT system for WFSG application

2 coupling capacitors and an auxiliary inductor, aiming to achieve resonance conditions; the ensuing current, rectified via a diode rectifier, is then used as power supply for the load. Resonant operation can permit to achieve soft switching, limiting the losses and permitting to increase the operative frequency. An integrated capacitive WPT for WFSM was investigated in [44] proposing to locate the system in the air gap of the machine without increasing its overall volume, whereas in [41] a prototype of an axial capacitive WPT was presented. Capacitive solutions for WFSM applications were investigated and compared with traditional rotor power coupling techniques in [43]. This study highlights advantages of CPT over traditional, methods, such as the field confinement without need of extra shielding, high mechanical integrity for efficient operation at various speeds, and the elimination of additional rotor components by placing the resonance coil in the stationary frame; however, it also mentions that, challenges like vibration and plate gap tolerances still need to be addressed. Whereas in [42] a comparison of inductive vs. capacitive WPT solutions is presented, demonstrating the viability of the latter, especially in thin-gap applications.

Finally, it can be said that capacitive WPT may be used for WFSM rotary applications, especially when low power is required, but it has not become popular because of several limitations: low power transfer capacity; high sensitivity to the positioning of the armatures; complex control required to ensure a proper operation, especially when resonance conditions are sought.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Synchronous machines are deemed to be a good choice as propulsion motors for EVs. Nevertheless, the use of PMSMs based on rare-earth magnets is increasingly questioned because of both environmental and procurement concerns, so the interest in WFSMs has grown despite the issues and limitations faced when using the classical sliprings-brushes solution for supplying the rotary field winding. This paper presented a brief overview of the main alternative technologies that have been proposed to overcome such problem by providing contactless solutions. Each of them presents specific pros and cons, so none of them has emerged yet as a clearly preferable solution; further research efforts are therefore necessary in order to achieve a better solution suited for application in EVs. Table

II presents a comprehensive comparison of key features associated with inductive power transfer, capacitive power transfer, and embedded winding methods for achieving brushless excitation of wound-field synchronous motors (WFSMs). These technologies effectively eliminate the need for brushes and slip rings, thereby enhancing reliability and reducing maintenance requirements. However, each approach exhibits a unique set of advantages and limitations, influencing their suitability for specific applications. The comparison highlights differences in power density, efficiency, complexity, and sensitivity to misalignment and air gaps, providing valuable insights for selecting the most appropriate excitation method based on performance requirements and design constraints.

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF BRUSHLESS POWER TRANSFER METHODS BASED ON VARIOUS FEATURES

Feature	Inductive Power Transfer	Capacitive Power Transfer	Embedded Winding Methods
High Power Density	✓	×	×
Efficient Field Control	✓	×	×
No Slip Rings or Brushes	✓	✓	✓
High Speed Capability	✓	✓	✓
Low Maintenance Requirements	✓	✓	✓
Complexity of Implementation	×	✓	✓
Sensitivity to Misalignment	✓	✓	×
High Efficiency	✓	×	×
Suitable for High Frequency	✓	✓	×
EMI Issues	✓	×	×
Cost-Effectiveness	×	✓	×

REFERENCES

- [1] A. März, P. Plötz, and P. Jochem, "Global perspective on co2 emissions of electric vehicles," *Environmental Research Letters*, vol. 16, no. 5, p. 054043, 2021.
- [2] International Energy Agency (IEA), "By 2030 evs represent more than 60% of vehicles sold globally, and require an adequate surge in chargers installed in buildings," 2022. Licence: CC BY 4.0.
- [3] R. Kawamoto, H. Mochizuki, Y. Moriguchi, T. Nakano, M. Motohashi, Y. Sakai, and A. Inaba, "Estimation of co2 emissions of internal combustion engine vehicle and battery electric vehicle using lca," *Sustainability*, vol. 11, no. 9, p. 2690, 2019.
- [4] J. Wang, X. Yuan, and K. Atallah, "Design optimization of a surface-mounted permanent-magnet motor with concentrated windings for electric vehicle applications," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 62, no. 3, pp. 1053–1064, 2012.
- [5] G. Delette, "Nd2fe14b permanent magnets substituted with non-critical light rare earth elements (ce, la): A review," *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, vol. 577, p. 170768, 2023.
- [6] S. Bose, B. Mizero, and P. A. Ariya, "Neodymium recovery from ndfeb magnets: a sustainable, instantaneous, and cost-effective method," *Green Chemistry*, vol. 26, no. 7, pp. 3909–3925, 2024.
- [7] IDTechEx, "Electric motors for electric vehicles 2025-2035: Technologies, materials, markets, and forecasts," 2024. Accessed: 2024-10-08.
- [8] F. Graffeo *et al.*, "Modeling and design of wound-field synchronous machines for transportation applications," 2023.
- [9] G. Pellegrino, A. Vagati, B. Boazzo, and P. Guglielmi, "Comparison of induction and pm synchronous motor drives for ev application including design examples," *IEEE Transactions on industry applications*, vol. 48, no. 6, pp. 2322–2332, 2012.
- [10] D. G. Dorrell, "Are wound-rotor synchronous motors suitable for use in high efficiency torque-dense automotive drives?," in *IECON 2012-38th Annual Conference on IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, pp. 4880–4885, IEEE, 2012.

- [11] A. K. Jain and V. Ranganathan, "Modeling and field oriented control of salient pole wound field synchronous machine in stator flux coordinates," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 58, no. 3, pp. 960–970, 2010.
- [12] S. M. Seyedi, D. Talebi, and H. A. Toliyat, "A pm-free brushless synchronous machine with a novel compensated wound-field excited by modulated rotating magnetic flux," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, pp. 1–12, 2024.
- [13] R. D. Hall and R. P. Roberge, "Carbon brush performance on slip rings," in *Conference Record of 2010 Annual Pulp & Paper Industry Technical Conference*, pp. 1–6, IEEE, 2010.
- [14] J. K. Nøland, S. Nuzzo, A. Tassarolo, and E. F. Alves, "Excitation system technologies for wound-field synchronous machines: Survey of solutions and evolving trends," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 109699–109718, 2019.
- [15] M. Pallantla, J. D. M. Deivanayagam, S. Thamballa, and N. Mohan, "A line commutated-thyristor bridge emulated rotating power electronic converter for brushless exciter applications," in *2020 IEEE 21st Workshop on Control and Modeling for Power Electronics (COMPEL)*, pp. 1–5, IEEE, 2020.
- [16] S. S. H. Rafin, Q. Ali, and T. A. Lipo, "A novel sub-harmonic synchronous machine using three-layer winding topology," *World Electric Vehicle Journal*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 16, 2022.
- [17] S. S. H. Bukhari, G. J. Sirewal, M. Ayub, and J.-S. Ro, "A new small-scale self-excited wound rotor synchronous motor topology," *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, vol. 57, no. 2, pp. 1–5, 2020.
- [18] D. Talebi, M. C. Gardner, S. M. Seyedi, and H. A. Toliyat, "An asynchronously excited brushless wound field synchronous machine," in *2022 International Conference on Electrical Machines (ICEM)*, pp. 2107–2113, IEEE, 2022.
- [19] L. Sun, X. Gao, F. Yao, Q. An, and T. Lipo, "A new type of harmonic current excited brushless synchronous machine based on an open winding pattern," in *2014 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)*, pp. 2366–2373, 2014.
- [20] C. Lecluyse, B. Minnaert, and M. Kleemann, "A review of the current state of technology of capacitive wireless power transfer," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 18, p. 5862, 2021.
- [21] A. M. Jawad, R. Nordin, S. K. Gharghan, H. M. Jawad, and M. Ismail, "Opportunities and challenges for near-field wireless power transfer: A review," *Energies*, vol. 10, no. 7, p. 1022, 2017.
- [22] Z. Popovic, "Near-and far-field wireless power transfer," in *2017 13th International Conference on Advanced Technologies, Systems and Services in Telecommunications (TELSIKS)*, pp. 3–6, IEEE, 2017.
- [23] D. A. Newaskar and B. Patil, "Wireless power transfer through inductive coupling for aimds," *power*, vol. 1, p. 4, 2019.
- [24] C. Stancu, T. Ward, K. M. Rahman, R. Dawsey, and P. Savagian, "Separately excited synchronous motor with rotary transformer for hybrid vehicle application," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 54, no. 1, pp. 223–232, 2017.
- [25] R. Manko, M. Vukotić, D. Makuc, D. Vončina, D. Miljavec, and S. Čorović, "Modelling of the electrically excited synchronous machine with the rotary transformer design influence," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 8, p. 2832, 2022.
- [26] MAHLE, "Mahle develops highly efficient magnet-free electric motor," <https://newsroom.mahle.com/press/en/press-releases/mahle-develops-highly-efficient-magnet-free-electric-motor-82368>, vol. 1, no. 1, 2021.
- [27] V. Rallabandi, B. Ozpineci, and P. Kumar, "How evs can escape the rare earth trap: Promising experimental motors are using exotic materials and ingenious configurations," *IEEE Spectrum*, vol. 61, no. 8, pp. 36–41, 2024.
- [28] T. Raminosa, R. H. Wiles, and J. Wilkins, "Novel rotary transformer topology with improved power transfer capability for high-speed applications," *IEEE transactions on industry applications*, vol. 56, no. 1, pp. 277–286, 2019.
- [29] L. Sun, J. Kang, Y. Liu, Z. Mao, and Z. Zhong, "Wireless power transfer based contactless excitation of electrically excited synchronous motor," in *2020 IEEE 9th International Power Electronics and Motion Control Conference (IPEMC2020-ECCE Asia)*, pp. 1091–1097, IEEE, 2020.
- [30] R. Trevisan and A. Costanzo, "A 1-kw contactless energy transfer system based on a rotary transformer for sealing rollers," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 61, no. 11, pp. 6337–6345, 2014.
- [31] D. Bortis, L. Fässler, A. Looser, and J. W. Kolar, "Analysis of rotary transformer concepts for high-speed applications," in *2013 Twenty-Eighth Annual IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition (APEC)*, pp. 3262–3269, IEEE, 2013.
- [32] J. Legranger, G. Friedrich, S. Vivier, and J. Mipo, "Comparison of two optimal rotary transformer designs for highly constrained applications," in *2007 IEEE International Electric Machines & Drives Conference*, vol. 2, pp. 1546–1551, IEEE, 2007.
- [33] A. Littau, B. Wagner, S. Köhler, A. Dietz, and S. Weber, "Design of inductive power transmission into the rotor of an externally excited synchronous machine," in *CoFAT*, 2014.
- [34] L. Xie, X. Yuan, J. Wang, and P. Mellor, "Design optimization of a rotary transformer converter for the excitation of electric machines," in *2023 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)*, pp. 5846–5852, IEEE, 2023.
- [35] N. Zietsman and N. Gule, "Design and evaluation of a 1.2 kva single phase rotary transformer," in *2016 XXII International Conference on Electrical Machines (ICEM)*, pp. 1466–1472, IEEE, 2016.
- [36] J. Legranger, G. Friedrich, S. Vivier, and J. C. Mipo, "Design of a brushless rotor supply for a wound rotor synchronous machine for integrated starter generator," in *2007 IEEE Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference*, pp. 236–241, IEEE, 2007.
- [37] M. Tosi, N. Bianchi, and H. Herzog, "Rotary transformer design for brushless electrically excited synchronous machines," *University of Padua, Padua*, 2014.
- [38] D. Bortis, I. Kovacevic, L. Fässler, and J. W. Kolar, "Optimization of rotary transformer for high-speed applications," in *2013 IEEE 14th workshop on control and modeling for power electronics (COMPEL)*, pp. 1–6, IEEE, 2013.
- [39] S.-A. Vip, J.-N. Weber, A. Rehfeldt, and B. Ponick, "Rotary transformer with ferrite core for brushless excitation of synchronous machines," in *2016 XXII International Conference on Electrical Machines (ICEM)*, pp. 890–896, IEEE, 2016.
- [40] Z. Xu and Q. JIANG, "Study of high frequency rotary transformer structures for contactless inductive power transfer," in *2019 22nd International Conference on Electrical Machines and Systems (ICEMS)*, pp. 1–5, IEEE, 2019.
- [41] A. Di Gioia, I. P. Brown, Y. Nie, R. Knippel, D. C. Ludois, J. Dai, S. Hagen, and C. Altheld, "Design and demonstration of a wound field synchronous machine for electric vehicle traction with brushless capacitive field excitation," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 54, no. 2, pp. 1390–1403, 2017.
- [42] J. Dai and D. C. Ludois, "A survey of wireless power transfer and a critical comparison of inductive and capacitive coupling for small gap applications," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 30, no. 11, pp. 6017–6029, 2015.
- [43] D. C. Ludois, J. K. Reed, and K. Hanson, "Capacitive power transfer for rotor field current in synchronous machines," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 27, no. 11, pp. 4638–4645, 2012.
- [44] S. Savio, S. M. H. Gillani, U. Pratik, R. Chattopadhyay, I. Husain, and Z. Pantic, "An integrated capacitive power transfer system for field excitation of wound field synchronous machine," in *2023 IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition (APEC)*, pp. 829–835, IEEE, 2023.